

total N content of rice seedlings was estimated by the Kjeldahl method and $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$ was determined using the Micromass 622 VG ISO gas mass spectrometer. The percent N derived from fertilizer ($^{15}\text{Ndff}$) and cyanobacteria ($^{15}\text{Ndfc}$) was calculated following the procedure of Pruden et al (1985).

Inoculation of cyanobacteria, either as immobilized or free-living along with urea, significantly increased N content and N uptake of rice seedlings (see table). Among the cultures, *N. muscorum* (DOH) immobilized in SCW with ^{15}N urea recorded the highest N content and N

uptake of rice seedlings. The rice seedlings receiving the immobilized culture have recorded higher N accumulation than the free-living cultures. In particular, the SCW-immobilized *N. muscorum* (DOH) contributed significantly higher N to rice seedlings (25.84%) than the other (see figure) by way of N_2 fixation, thereby recording a high N transfer efficiency. The results revealed that 16–28% of N can be added to rice seedlings by immobilized cyanobacteria in the presence of urea as fertilizer N (Valiente et al 2000).

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Nitrogen contribution by immobilized cyanobacteria to rice seedlings (cultivar ADT36) grown under hydroponic conditions.

$T_1 = A. azollae$ (AS-DS-SK) (free); $T_2 = A. azollae$ (AS-DS-SK) (PUF); $T_3 = A. azollae$ (AS-DS-SK) (SCW); $T_4 = N. muscorum$ (DOH) (free); $T_5 = N. muscorum$ (DOH) (PUF); $T_6 = N. muscorum$ (DOH) (SCW); $T_7 = ^{15}\text{N}$ urea. (All treatments received ^{15}N urea uniformly as uninoculated control.)

% Ndff and %Ndfc were calculated as follows (Pruden et al 1985):

$$\% \text{Ndff} = \frac{\text{Percent } ^{15}\text{N} \text{ atom excess in inoculated plant}}{\text{Percent } ^{15}\text{N} \text{ atom excess in uninoculated plant}} \times 100$$

$$\% \text{Ndfc} = 100 - \% \text{Ndff}$$

Evaluation and identification of cold-tolerant rice genotypes by cold-water irrigation stress

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In temperate regions, rice is cultivated as a summer crop. However, several million hectares in temperate and high-altitude areas cannot be planted with modern rice varieties

because of low-temperature stress at different stages of plant growth. Low temperatures below 15°C during the vegetative stage cause leaf discoloration, reduce tillering, and delay heading

(Rutger and Peterson 1979). During the reproductive stage, low night temperature causes sterility, leading to a 20% yield loss (Li et al 1997, Kwon et al 2002). In South Korea, low-

temperature stress is the main limiting factor for rice productivity. The main challenge is to identify appropriate solutions to low-temperature stress in rice. This study has been undertaken to evaluate 69 advanced breeding lines of the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) along with five Korean rice cultivars using the cold-water-temperature irrigation facility developed at the Chuncheon substation of NICS, RDA, Republic of Korea, to identify promising cold-tolerant genotypes for use as donors in their temperate rice improvement program through molecular genetics and breeding research.

The 69 IRRI lines consisted of 51 new plant types (NPT) and 18 bred for high-altitude areas (HAA) of the Philippines. Korean rice cultivars Jinbubyeo and Odaebyeo were used as cold-tolerant checks and Saesbeolbyeo was the cold-sensitive check. The IRRI breeding lines, along with Korean varieties, were planted in single rows each and consisted of 40 plants at a spacing of 30 cm × 15 cm. Irrigation water temperature was normal until tillering stage. Water temperature regimes ranging from 17, 18, 19, and 25 °C were set and continuous flowing water of 5-cm depth was maintained from tillering to maturity. Leaf

discoloration was scored during the vegetative stage and data on four agronomic traits—culm length (cm), panicle exertion (cm), panicle length (cm), and spikelet sterility (%)—were collected at the end of the stress period for the selected 12 breeding lines. Traits were evaluated using the *Standard evaluation methods of rice* (RDA 1995).

Of the 69 IRRI breeding lines tested at four temperature regimes, five NPT lines and two lines adapted to HAA did not express leaf discoloration. The plants stayed green throughout the growth period. The remaining 62 IRRI lines were highly

Genotypes and performance of four agronomic traits in each temperature regime.^a

Variety/genotype	Culm length (cm)				Panicle length (cm)			
	17 °C	18 °C	19 °C	25 °C	17 °C	18 °C	19 °C	25 °C
Geumobyseo	51.0 ^d	54.0 ^c	57.0 ^{cd}	69.6 ^{de}	15.4 ^{ef}	16.6 ^{de}	16.8 ^{cd}	19.0 ^f
Sangjubyseo	49.2 ^d	49.2 ^d	55.4 ^d	67.4 ^{ef}	16.4 ^{de}	17.0 ^d	16.8 ^{cd}	19.0 ^f
Jinbubyseo	56.2 ^c	59.2 ^b	59.2 ^{cd}	72.4 ^d	14.6 ^f	15.4 ^e	15.2 ^e	17.6 ^{fg}
Odaebyeo	58.4 ^c	61.0 ^b	63.8 ^b	70.0 ^{de}	15.4 ^{ef}	16.8 ^{de}	15.8 ^{de}	16.6 ^g
Saesbeolbyseo	27.8 ^h	27.2 ^h	30.6 ^h	51.6 ^g	16.8 ^{de}	16.2 ^{de}	17.0 ^{cd}	18.8 ^f
IR61727-4B-1-1-1	73.6 ^a	76.6 ^a	84.0 ^a	113.0 ^a	19.4 ^b	20.6 ^{bc}	20.4 ^b	23.4 ^{cd}
IR64629-5-3-2-2	65.0 ^b	59.2 ^b	66.0 ^b	88.0 ^b	21.8 ^a	21.8 ^{ab}	22.4 ^a	27.6 ^a
IR66160-121-4-4-2	41.8 ^e	44.8 ^e	51.0 ^e	68.6 ^{de}	17.2 ^{cd}	17.4 ^d	18.0 ^c	21.4 ^e
IR69132-17-2-2-2	38.2 ^f	38.6 ^{fg}	43.2 ^f	77.4 ^c	19.4 ^b	20.6 ^{bc}	20.2 ^b	24.0 ^{bcd}
IR70554-48-1-2	31.2 ^g	40.6 ^f	41.4 ^f	69.2 ^{de}	18.8 ^{bc}	20.4 ^{bc}	20.8 ^b	23.0 ^{de}
IR71218-7-1-2	29.2 ^{gh}	36.4 ^g	35.2 ^g	62.6 ^f	20.0 ^b	20.0 ^c	20.4 ^b	25.0 ^{bc}
IR72225-20-3-2-3	31.6 ^g	39.0 ^{fg}	43.8 ^f	69.6 ^{de}	22.2 ^a	22.6 ^a	23.8 ^a	25.6 ^b
MSE	4.78	7.31	7.49	14.76	1.65	1.39	1.40	2.08
LSD	2.78	3.44	3.48	4.89	1.63	1.50	1.50	1.84

Variety/genotype	Panicle exertion (cm)				Sterility (%)			
	17 °C	18 °C	19 °C	25 °C	17 °C	18 °C	19 °C	25 °C
Geumobyseo	2.6 ^a	3.8 ^a	4.6 ^{ab}	5.8 ^{bc}	40.5 ^c	8.1 ^e	7.0 ^{de}	4.2 ^d
Sangjubyseo	1.6 ^a	2.6 ^{ab}	2.8 ^c	6.2 ^{bc}	23.7 ^d	12.0 ^{de}	5.2 ^e	4.7 ^d
Jinbubyseo	2.2 ^a	3.8 ^a	3.2 ^{bc}	5.0 ^{cd}	12.4 ^e	8.0 ^e	5.7 ^e	2.5 ^d
Odaebyeo	1.6 ^a	2.6 ^{ab}	5.0 ^{ab}	4.4 ^{cd}	33.0 ^{cd}	28.4 ^c	16.7 ^{cd}	3.7 ^d
Saesbeolbyseo	-9.0 ^c	-9.8 ^d	-6.8 ^f	-1.2 ^e	100.0 ^a	100.0 ^a	98.8 ^a	10.1 ^{cd}
IR61727-4B-1-1-1	2.6 ^a	1.2 ^b	6.6 ^a	11.0 ^a	28.5 ^d	20.1 ^{cd}	13.4 ^{cde}	10.8 ^{cd}
IR64629-5-3-2-2	2.2 ^a	1.8 ^{ab}	3.2 ^{bc}	12.8 ^a	98.2 ^a	95.1 ^a	76.3 ^b	12.3 ^{cd}
IR66160-121-4-4-2	-2.8 ^b	-2.2 ^c	0.4 ^d	4.6 ^{cd}	86.9 ^b	57.2 ^b	21.4 ^c	6.8 ^d
IR69132-17-2-2-2	-9.0 ^c	-8.2 ^d	-9.4 ^g	5.6 ^{bcd}	100.0 ^a	100.0 ^a	99.6 ^a	66.8 ^a
IR70554-48-1-2	-7.2 ^c	-4.2 ^c	-4.4 ^e	8.2 ^b	100.0 ^a	99.1 ^a	97.6 ^a	33.8 ^b
IR71218-7-1-2	-12.4 ^d	-12.4 ^e	-8.4 ^{fg}	3.0 ^d	100.0 ^a	99.1 ^a	99.9 ^a	26.3 ^{bc}
IR72225-20-3-2-3	-13.6 ^d	-9.4 ^d	-13.2 ^h	-1.4 ^e	99.3 ^a	99.6 ^a	99.6 ^a	73.1 ^a
MSE	4.34	3.73	2.90	4.31	57.4	56.4	67.1	209.3
LSD	2.64	2.46	2.17	2.64	9.63	9.55	10.4	18.4

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significant at the 5% level by least significant difference test.

sensitive to low temperature, showing leaf discoloration and poor agronomic traits, and were not considered for data analysis. The performance of the four agronomic traits showed direct correlation with temperature regime. The temperature regimes of 17 °C and 18 °C had severely affected the normal expression of agronomic traits on all rice genotypes. Therefore, we have considered 19 °C water temperature as the critical temperature for the identification of cold-tolerant genotypes. In this temperature regime, the breeding lines IR61727-4B-1-1-1 and IR61660-121-4-4-2 did not show a significant reduction in the traits

during the stress period (see table). The reproductive-stage low-temperature stress caused high sterility of spikelets in all lines, except IR61727-4B-1-1-1 and IR66160-121-4-4-2, which had 13% and 21% sterility, respectively, compared with the cold-tolerant japonica varieties Jinbubyeo (6%) and Odaebyeo (17%) (see table). Low temperature had a negative effect on the development of panicles. As a result of low-temperature stress, 62 IRRI breeding lines had degenerated panicles (see figure). The breeding lines IR61727-4B-1-1-1 and IR66160-121-4-4-2 were identified as the most promising genotypes for cold tolerance. The

results demonstrated that these breeding lines represent a new source of tolerance for low-temperature stress that could broaden the genetic base of temperate rice cultivars grown in Korea. These two genotypes may also be suitable for boro rice cultivation in the eastern regions of India and Bangladesh.

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Degenerate panicles of a low-temperature-sensitive line at the time of flowering.

Benefits of growing azolla under a space-sharing method

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In present-day agriculture, even though yield of cereals has increased in harmony with population growth (Bockman 1997), long-term productivity of the soil, particularly in rice fields, has been neglected. To cope with this situation, an attempt was made to replenish the depleted

soil N in every season by growing azolla with rice. Under a space-sharing method, a separate space is allotted for rice and azolla. The aim is to offer enough space for the simultaneous growth of azolla in the field and to realize benefits from this approach—effective nutrient turnover, weed control,

and more sunlight for rice.

The field experiments were conducted during the wet season (Oct 2001-Jan 2002) in the wetlands of TNAU. The experimental soil (Vertic Ustochrept) was clay (68.6%) and has a pH of 8.2, electrical conductivity 0.66 dS m⁻¹, organic C 0.62%, 242 kg